

Effect of Wet-Heat on Seed germination of *Parkia biglobosa* (Jacq Benth) (African Locust bean), *Prosopis africana*(Guill&Perr) (Nigerian Iron wood) and *Piliostigma thonningii* (Schumach) (Monkey'sbread) from the Derived Savanna Zone of Nigeria.

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Abstract

Seed germination determines the success of most wild plants in the savanna agroecosystem. Seed dormancy is common among wild plants. This research was therefore carried out to determine the effect of wet-heat on seed germination of some savanna seeds with hard seed coatings in order to justify the effect of annual bush burning in savanna. The fruits of *Parkia biglobosa*, *Prosopis africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* were collected from the mentioned trees in April, March and February during their respective harvesting periods at Egume and Anyigba in Kogi state, Nigeria. Effect of wet heat on the seed germination of these savanna trees was tested by placing ten (10) seeds each in boiling water (100°C) and removed at timed interval of 1,2,3,4,5 and 6 second(s) respectively. The percentage germination of the seeds treated with hot water gave a significantly ($P < 0.05$) highest germination of 40% in *P. biglobosa* for 4 seconds, 42% and 34% in *P. africana* and *P. thonningii* for 5 seconds respectively. Highest germination in terms of plant height (cm) and the number of leaves was observed in *P. biglobosa* after 15 days, while that of *Prosopis* and *Piliostigma* were observed after 18 days. There was no germination among the control seeds of each group of trees at the initial period of the experiment implies that wet-heat treatment had a great effect on *P. biglobosa*, *P. africana* and *P. thonningii* seeds germination.

Keywords; Dormancy, germination, Savanna, seeds, treatment, wet-heat

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Introduction

The direct effect of fire is the release of heat to the environment. For fire-prone environments, dry heat has long been recognized as an effective cue for breaking dormancy in seeds of a number of species (Light and van Staden, 2004). It mainly acts on seeds with physical dormancy by cracking the seed coat or splitting the palisade layer of the micropyle, although some physiological effects on seed embryo have been documented. Indeed, heat has been suggested to regulate germination in some seeds, through the release or induction of physiological dormancy [Denton *et al.*, 2013]. This has been further corroborated by many experimental studies [Clarke *et al.*, 2000; Gashaw and Michelsen, 2002; Schelin *et al.*, 2003]. The effect of heat on seed germination is highly dependent on temperature and different species have different minimum temperature requirements and different thresholds at which heat may become lethal to them. Moreover, studies on germination responses to heat shock [Herranz *et al.*, 1998; Zida *et al.*, 2008] have revealed that

not only the amount of heat reaching the seeds, but also the duration of seeds' exposure to a given temperature is important.

Seed dormancy is common in wild plants [especially in weeds], where it may ensure the ability of a species to survive natural catastrophes, decrease competition between individual of the same species, or prevent germination out of season [Finkelstein *et al.* 2008]. Dormant seed does not have the capacity to germinate in a specified period of time under any combination of normal physical environmental factors that are otherwise favourable for its germination, i.e. after the seed becomes nondormant [Finch-Savage, 2006]. All types of dormancy impose a delay between seed shedding and germination, but the underlying causes may vary. This research is therefore aimed at determining the effect of wet-heat on the germination of three Savanna seeds with hard seed coatings .This is to justify the effect of annual bush burning in Savanna, since some seeds in Savanna will not germinate unless treated with high temperature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Determination of the Effect of Heat treatment on the germination of some savanna seeds

Seed and Processing

The fruits of *Parkia biglobosa*, *Prosopis Africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* were collected from the mentioned trees in April, March and February during their respective harvesting periods at Egume around Anyigba, Kogi State. The seeds of these savanna trees were selected on the basis of the hard nature of their seed coatings and their ability to remain in the state of dormancy over a long period amongst other species. The husks of the pods, the dry brown indehiscent pods [Sacande and sanogo, 2007] of *P. biglobosa* were opened along the suture manually to remove the seeds together with the yellow pulp. The pulps were washed off from the seeds in a big clay-sieve in water. The pods of *P. africana* and *P. thonningii* after harvesting were sun-dried for two weeks and they were opened to releases the seeds by the use of local pestle and mortar. All the seeds were sun-dried and placed under three (3) groups (i.e. A= *P. biglobosa*, B=*P. africana*, and C=*P. thonningii*). The viability of the seeds was tested in accordance with the methods of Germ [1975] and Copeland [1976].

Effect of wet heat treatment on the seeds

The effect of wet heat on the seeds of the mentioned savanna trees was tested by placing ten (10) seeds each of these trees (groups) on a folded wire gauze with a handle; the seeds were then dipped in boiling water (100⁰C) and removed at timed intervals of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 second(s) respectively. The seeds were then allowed to cool by soaking in water bath for 5 minutes. Another ten seeds of each group were not dipped into hot water and were used as the control. Effect of wetting and drying of the seeds was tested by placing the ten seeds of each group including the control seeds-(i.e. seven replicates of seventy see ds) in 7 beakers containing water bath for 24 hours. The seeds were removed and placed on white papers and sun-dried. Therefore, the seeds of each category alongside with their control were sown in poly pots, two seeds per pot. The sowing dept was 2cm deep for all the replicates. Watering of the seeds was done and the seed s were considered to have germinated when the tips of the radicles have grown free of the seed coats. The mean height of the seedlings and the average number of leaves for each plant category was also taken at the interval of 3 days after germination .The number of leaves was calculated using the formular prescribed by Abubakar and Maimuna [2013].

$$NL = \frac{Tnl}{Tnsem}$$

Where: NL = Number of leaves

Tnl = Total number of leaves on a particular plant

Tnsem = Total number of seeds emerged.

Data obtained during the study were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the mean values were compared using T-test according to the method described by Steel and Torrie [1980] using a Statistical Software package for Social sciences (SPSS) version 19.

RESULTS

Effect of wet heat on the rate of Germination of Savanna Seeds

The results for the percentage mean germination and the rate of germination (ie height and number of leaves) of the savanna seeds sown after six days under wet heat treatment is presented in Table 1 and 2 respectively. The results showed how the seeds of 3 different savanna trees responded in terms of germination to different times(s) of heating (wet heat). A total number of 81 percent seeds germination were recorded during the study, 30 percent seeds germination was recorded for the seeds of *P. biglobosa*, 27 for the seed of *P. africana* and 24 percent was recorded for the seeds of *P. thonningii*. The results revealed the optimum duration(s) of heating for the germination of the seeds, 4 seconds for the seeds of *P. biglobosa* and 5 seconds for the germination of *P. africana* and *P. thonningii*. The results also showed a steady increase in seed germination along side with the duration of heating, and percentage rate of seed germination started decreasing after the optimum heating periods (figure1).

The results have also shown the average height (cm) and the number of leaves (NL) emerged by the experimented seeds six days after sowing. The average height (cm) and the number of leaves (NL) emerged for all the seeds of the experimented plants increased steadily as the days of observation increased. The average height (cm) (148.7) and the number of leaves (84) recorded against the seeds of *P. biglobosa* were significantly ($P < 0.05$) highest at 18 days after sowing, followed by the seeds of *P. africana*. The control seeds of the 3 plants species did not show any form of germination until 15 days after sowing the seeds of *P. biglobosa*, and 18 days after sowing the seeds of *P. africana* and *P. thonningii*.

Figure 1: A graph showing the effect of wet heat on the germination of savanna seeds sown after 6 days

Plate 1: Showing the Seedling of *Piliostigma thonningii* after 28 days

Plate 2: Showing the Seedling of *Prosopis Africana* after 28days

Plate 3: Showing the Seedling of *Parkia biglobosa* after 25days

Table 2: Effect of Wet-heat on the germination of Savanna seeds Sown after Six days

% Mean germination of Savanna of seed of				
Heating Duration (s)	<i>P. biglobosa</i>	<i>P. africana</i>	<i>P. thonningii</i>	Total (%)
0 (control)	0	0	0	0
1	4	2	2	8
2	5	3	3	11
3	5	4	3	12
4	8	6	6	20
5	5	8	7	20
6	3	4	3	10
Total	30	7	24	81

Note; Number of seeds sown per each category is 10, P-value =0.4531 at 5% level of significance

S = Second

Table 2: Average height (cm) and the Number of Leaves per Observation Day Emerged by the Experimental Seeds Six Days after Sowing

Contact observation day	<i>P. biglobosa</i> Height (cm)	NL	<i>P. africana</i> Height (cm)	NL	<i>P. thonningii</i> Height (cm)	NL
3	5.20	18	5.10	16	4.00	4
6	10.40	32	10.20	30	8.80	8
9	17.30	48	16.00	46	11.30	12
12	27.90	66	26.90	62	24.0	16
15	38.40(5.1)	74(18)	38.80	72	30.0	24
18	48.70	84	47.30(50)	80(16)	32.0(4.10)	28(4)

Note: NL = Number of leaves, P-value =0.4320 at 5% level of significance

Values in parentheses represented the height (cm) and numbers of leaves for the control of each plant.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Heat on the Germination of Savanna Seeds

It is a known fact that, all viable seeds have ability to germinate if place under suitable conditions necessary for germination. While in certain plants such seeds will immediately germinate after harvest, in others they fail to germinate for sometimes even when placed under such conditions that are ordinarily favourable for germination either due to some internal factors or due to specific requirements for some environmental factors [Dayamba *et al.*, 2008].

The seeds of the tree species: *Parkia biglobosa*, *Prosopis africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* have been observed to exhibit physical dormancy due to hardness of their seed coats which apparently seemed to have imposed high heat resistance on non-dominant embryo or to block water uptake or influx of oxygen into the internal parts of the seed. This work agrees with Finkelstein *et al.*, [2008] that seed dormancy is common in wild plants especially *Parkia biglobosa*, *Prosopis africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* where it may ensure the ability of the species to survive natural catastrophes.

The percentage germination of the seed of these agro forest plant species treated with hot water [wet heat] gave a significantly ($P < 0.05$) highest germination of 40% in *Parkia biglobosa*, for 4 seconds, 42% and 34% in *Prosopis africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* respectively for 5 seconds. The percentage germination differences among the seeds may be attributed to the variation in the hardness of their protective coverings (the seed coats) or the enclosed embryo. This suggested that, *Parkia biglobosa* and *Prosopis africana* have the hardest protective covering (the seed coat). Investigations carried out by Agboola and Etejere [1991], Agboola and Adedire [1998], Sabongari [2001] and Aliero [2004] revealed

that, a sudden dip of dry seeds in boiling or hot water bath may lead to the ruapture of seed coat tissues causing physiological changes and subsequent germination of the embryo.

Among the seed dormancy treatment with hot water, the highest germination in terms of the plant height (cm) and the number of leaves emergence was observed in *Parkia* after 15 days earlier than *Prosopis* and *Piliostigma* which emerged after 18 days of the experiment. It was also observed that, there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in germination rate in terms of plant height (cm), the number of leaves and the days of germination among the seeds. The germination decreased however, when the various seeds were allowed in hot water for a very long period. This implied that the embryo of the seeds may have been got destroyed following contact with hot water for a prolonged period as reported by Sabongari [2001], Dayamba *et al.*, [2010] and Abubakar and Maimuna [2013].

At the initial period of the experiment (sowing) there was no evidence of germination in the control seeds. This may have been due to the fact that, water was not made available for the embryos to germinate. Along the experiment, the untreated (control) seeds also germinated but it took them a long period of 15 days for *Parkia*, and 18 days for *Prosopis* and *Piliostigma* after sowing. This gave rise to the shorter height of seedlings in the control as compared to those treated with hot water (wet-heat). This means that, wet- heat treatment had a great effect on *Parkia biglobosa*, *Prosopis africana* and *Piliostigma thonningii* seeds germination.

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